

Report on the First NFDI Berlin-Brandenburg network meeting

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The first NFDI in Berlin-Brandenburg (NFDI.BB) meeting was aimed at setting up a network of all NFDI consortia located within the region. The meeting was held at the Weierstrass Institute (WIAS) in the center of Berlin on Oct 12, 2023 from 10am to 4:30pm. The main goal was to establish contacts between the members of the different consortia and identify common fields of interest. Particular focus was on the mutual benefit of cooperation between the projects from consortia in different disciplines.

25 out of the 27 consortia of the NFDI are present within the Berlin-Brandenburg region, involving more than 120 scientific and other institutions. 73 registered participants were to attend the meeting. Most participants belonged to one of the 21 different consortia of the NFDI (see figure below), whereas a few (“other”) were affiliated to no consortiums but attended with interest in learning about the NFDI and its consortia. Note that a few participants belonged to more than one consortium.

While similar NFDI local communities (“Stammtische”) exist in a few other regions in Germany, a formal network of these communities is still elusive and is expected to be initiated by the NFDI headquarter in the future.

The agenda of the workshop consisted of two main parts, both of which were designed to be interactive.

The morning session focused on the introduction of participants and getting to know each other. Each consortium was asked to answer the following 4 questions:

- What is specific to your NFDI Consortium?
- Are your colleagues aware of the importance of research data management or what kind of excuses do they have for not considering it?
- How many consortia do you cooperate with (actual number vs. proposed)?
- What would you like to achieve in this meeting?

Figure 1: Participants Statistics

The subsequent brainstorming discussion served to identify topics for the World Café that took place in the afternoon. Several topics were suggested, both by the organizers and the participants. The top 5 topics voted by the participants were:

- Acceptance and Importance of FAIR principles and Research Data Management (RDM). Outreach outside the NFDI bubble? Acceptance of stakeholders
- Open-source Software. Used infrastructure technology? Longevity | long term services in NFDI

- Teaching RDM and literacy in the use of cross disciplinary data types
- Industry and International Collaborations
- Ontologies and Knowledge Graphs (KG)

The afternoon started with two parallel World Café sessions where participants picked 3 (out of 5) topics to discuss in small rounds. Afterwards, the facilitators reported from their World Café tables, followed by a general wrap-up. Among others, the following points were discussed:

- Organization of present and future work: Who is responsible for the individual measures? The consortia individually or all the consortia together (bottom up strategy) or the bodies of the NFDI (top down strategy)?
- Lack of awareness about the NFDI sections (departments of the NFDI Association (“Verein”)) where cross-sectional topics should be investigated across the boundaries of the consortia. Their role, and the communication channels involved, was not clear to several participants
- Importance of teaching the central topics of the NFDI such as RDM and KG, mainly to scientists in early phases of their career. Role of incentives for engagement in data management
- More communication within and between the consortia. For example, it turned out that several consortia did not know (the number of) their cooperation partners, see also the Appendix
- Availability of infrastructure such as providing internet services and/or human resources for the NFDI. This issue is expected to become more important upon transition from development of concepts to providing long term services

Summary and next steps

Essentially, the first network meeting of the NFDI consortia in Berlin and Brandenburg met its intended goal. Overall, the atmosphere was open and constructive, with a focus on bridging traditional gaps and fostering interdisciplinary cooperation. The meeting enabled us to find a common language

and identify common fields of interest, with an emphasis on the overarching aspects of the NFDI. To this end, we can expect future collaborations on topics central to the NFDI, meeting either in smaller groups to discuss topics such as teaching RDM or ontologies, to having biannual meetings in a bigger fora.

Contact

- For feedback on this report, and for suggesting future meeting topics, email: nfdi_bb@mardi4nfdi.de
- A NFDI_BB mailing list was created, and the participants were asked to register
https://www.listserv.dfn.de/sympa/info/nfdi_bb
Note that this list will be used as the main communication channel for information on future NFDI_BB activities

Appendix

Introduction of participants and getting to know each other Participants introduce themselves guided by the following 4 questions:

1. What is specific to your NFDI consortium?
2. Are your colleagues aware of the importance of research data management or what kind of excuses do they have for not considering it?
3. How many consortia do you cooperate with (actual number vs. proposed)?
4. What would you like to achieve in this meeting?

Consortium	Question 1	Question 2	Question 3	Question 4
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KonsortSWD	network of 42 research data centers that provide data for social, economic, behavioral and educational research	yes & no	8	getting to know the people
Text+	text based data → collections → lexical resources → digital editions	yes & no it's a lot of work on top of research, sharing is difficult	1 vs. 4	networking
NFDI4Culture	consortium for research data on material and immaterial cultural heritage Target groups: architecture, art history, musicology, theater, dance, film, media studies, DH, GLAM	yes, most of them are excuses: not enough resources, lack of information, unsure concerning legal topics	cooperate with ID consortia (more in the cross sections) ⁵⁶ participants are members of 25 different consortia	Get to know the NFDI universe not only (but also) the Digital Humanities bubble

NFDI4Objects	research data infrastructure for the material remains of human history	partly, some are holding curated digital collections, some have less contact with digital methods	NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Memory, Text+->cooperation in the makingplanned also BASEany that is building a core ontology within the NFDI	networking + collaborationto meet people doing the actual workexchange about topics
NFDI4Memory	By far the largest consortium → it is not only RDM → “Datafication” → historical work, material of contextualization	at the target audienceno established notion of “data”no established culture of RDM	Memorandum of understanding	Linking to other consortia learn from new experiences → do not repeat mistakes setup of communication channels- to the other consortia- to the NFDI Verein
NFDI4DS	scientific areas from social sciences, life sciences, natural sciences, engineering sciences- data science & artificial intelligence	aware: YESability: varies muchskills trainingcon- vince	NFDI4Cat(Base4NFDI)(NFDI)	(NFDIxCS) foster cooperation find synergies

NFDI4Ing	organizational structure with 7 Archetypes and 5 community clusters- Archetypes: representative for different fields of research in engineering- Community clusters: gateway to the community for dissemination of results and identification of requirements very heterogeneous topics: lab experiments, field experiments, simulations, research software, HPC,..	awareness is slowly increasing excuses: too much overhead; too little time no incentives missing expertise large number of different approaches/tools	As of August 2023: engaged in 19 collaborations -> second most active consortium (after Chem) in terms of collaborations with other consortia	identify overlapping needs and activities use synergies to avoid duplicate efforts
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NFDIxCS	It will/could be involved in all the other consortia = RDMCx = Cross Computer Science means that it not only creates solutions for but also with Computer Science Community and CS methods. Also consider software artifacts x computer science methods as data themselves and not only used these methods to generate and store/manage data. Take into account the different needs and use cases of the various computer science and disciplines	most of them are aware of the importance awareness is probably higher than in other disciplines	NFDI4DS NFDI4Ing MaRDI Base4NFDI	initiate strengthen an active cooperation learn from others
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FAIRagro	Geoinformation data Legal aspects -> data from private land Different scales Multidisciplinary: soil, environmental data, weather Legacy data e.g. from field book of long-term experiments	spatial yes, some no. some have never heard of RDM before, a few are quite interested in RDM and getting access to data of others, some are aware of RDM and refuse to make their data FAIR RDM is not applied because: it takes too much time and effort no one will be interested in our data there is no benefit to publishing data, only downsides the data belong to me someone else might use the data to publish without me	Common infrastructures, metadata, standards, DataPLANT Helpdesk: 4earth, 4bio-div, 4object-s Training: 4earth, 4bio-div, 4objects Ontologies: dataplant- Data stewards: 4earth, 4health, 4objects Legal aspects: 4health, 4Chem, 4ing, KonsortSWD Data continuous implementation (slowly) NFDIxCSim-age data: 4BIOIMAGE administrative: 4Memory	NETWORKING! to find out how to convince colleagues to participate in the activities of the different consortia! identify similar challenges & work together on urgently needed solutions+++ exchange of experiences -> on the organizational level identify cross-consortia needs, e.g. services, trainings, communication, tool, e.t.c. who has expertise/experience where?
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NFDI4Microbiota	working with any kind of microbiota historically very difficult fields health → human health → animal environment → terrestrial environment->marine	50%-80% aware structures and training is missing no time too complicated don't know how to start	14 different consortia many interactions in life and natural sciences	do networking get ideas of possible intersections, especially not from life sciences
NFDI4Immuno	data protection laws DSGVO no existing data infrastructure (in Germany) thematically relative homogeneous	awareness is present but knowledge and resources are missing in present culture of big scale data sharing	most life science consortia contract with Bioimage, Microbiota, GHGA, Health	networking identify synergies learn from experience of "older" consortia
NFDI4Health	studies and registries Epidemiological & clinical & health	more aware of RDM (maybe not clear about the importance) very time consuming where do you draw the line	not aware of cooperating consortia	connections with other/all overlaps with other consortia drive to delve into practical exercises & existing tools

NFDI4Biodiversity	broad with a lot of different disciplines and data + interdisciplinary evolved out of Gesellschaft für Biodiversität GFBio (DFG)	yes, they are aware However, a lot of isolated solutions exist	NFDI4Biodiversity? NFDI4Health NFDI4Chem Base4NFDI NFDI Sections Metadata, Terminologies, Provenance Proposed: Agro, Earth, DataScience	Networking Learn about others + identify synergies collaborate on terminology services (OntoPortal)+ Research Data Commons (RDC)
DAPHNE4NFDI	diversitybottom up vs top downlarge scale facilities vs user groupsno defined scientific field but rather a set of exp. methods	no easy answer!as a large scale facility, we provide services to our usersuser expectations differ a lot	FAIRmat NFDI4cat	Get to know each other
FAIRmat	Materials“mainly atom-istic”... up to mesoscale → prep. → exp. → sim.NOMAD	important: yes!excuses: a lab needs a dedicated person to do the data handling → hard to find and expensive → reduce barriers to RDM	“Physical sciences consortia” DAPHNE, Matwerk, 4Cat, 4Chem, PUNCH	...just curious

NFDI4Cat	very diverse disciplines strong industry involvement adapting overall infrastructure to existing laboratories & solutions → integrating them (not enforcing a single solution) integration of catalysis and catalysis-related sciences	YES the majority knows about the importance but implementing these systems into the everyday workflow is still complicated and needs some convincing	NFDI4Chem FAIRmat NFDI4Ing NFDI4DS we love to connect to more consortia	getting to know how other consortia solve similar problems we face find similarities, connection points and starting points for collaboration
MaRDI	what is mathematical data -> variable existence of proofs mainly formalized / abstract mathematics is seen as methods x cutting	no standards not required for publications mostly no we don't have data -> definition to data -> files, classical definition I can remember everything I know it ref to a proof with the initials of a retired person	3 (eng) + 3 (social) + 3(others WIP) ~ = 9	a break from work + free thermos! collaboration new local cooperation/common project + infrastructure what need does math fill? in other disciplines

NFDI4Chem	Diversity and Disciplinarity is large amount and kind of meta-data highly dynamic	~1/5 are experts in their respective domain the rest either think they are experts or are “the exception”	Cat, Matwerk, Fairmat, Ing, many more	Networking, best practice step towards “possible” harmonisation
NFDI4Earth	combines Earth data with Geochemical, Geomicrobiology, Biodiversity, Engineering, Big data, long-tail data, historical data	RDM involved are aware, others not so much Data received after processed data are often not preserved	Min 5 NFDI4Biodiversity NFDI4Microbiota NFDI4Culture Base4NFDI NFDI4Energy	Networking New collaborations

World Cafe Documentation

1. Acceptance and Importance of FAIR principles and Research Data Management (RDM). Outreach outside the NFDI bubble? Acceptance of stakeholders
2. Open-source Software. Used infrastructure technology? Longevity | long term services in NFDI
3. Teaching RDM and literacy in the use of cross disciplinary data types
4. Industry and International Collaborations
5. Ontologies and Knowledge Graphs

Figure 2: Acceptance and Importance of FAIR principles and Research Data Management (RDM). Outreach outside the NFDI bubble? Acceptance of stakeholders

Figure 5: Open-source Software. Used infrastructure technology? Longevity | long term services in NFDI

Figure 6: Open-source Software. Used infrastructure technology? Longevity | long term services in NFDI

Figure 7: Teaching RDM and literacy in the use of cross disciplinary data types

Figure 8: Teaching RDM and literacy in the use of cross disciplinary data types

Figure 9: Teaching RDM and literacy in the use of cross disciplinary data types

Figure 10: Teaching RDM and literacy in the use of cross disciplinary data types

⑧ WIAS
 3) International + industry collaboration

Industry → first have to organize

German, EU, International regn.

Valentia (NFDI general)

Technical level
 GAYA-X

↳ Architecture

Registers

↳ Re3data

↳ ORCID

↳ ROR

↳ IGSN

↳ Data Cite

- Multy-lingual data

- Earth data

- Mathematic data

- Cultural Har.

- Demographic data

- Biodiversity

- Computer science

EOSC

↳ conferences

↳ Workshops

↳ Projects

↳ Trainings

↳ international aspects

What it is? International standardization
 data governance

Research data level

RDA

↳ RDA-DA

↳ What are the outcomes

German

English

workshops conferences

outreach concept for presenting NFDI

↳ internationally

↳ speakers - to mediate answer questions

↳ success stories

Use cases best practice (stories)

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Figure 12: Industry and International Collaborations

Ontologies of Knowledge Graphs

Thomas (N. 11.11.17)

Figure 13: Ontologies and Knowledge Graphs

13 Ontologies & Knowledge Graphs

Chances (Mod 11)

benefits should be made clear

What do we need for
one NFDI KG?

- standards
- core entities

Do we need one
KG?
- common language
- connectors
are "enough"

Upper Level Ontology

one system for all which fits OK

Permanent Infrastructure + maintenance

DFG Guideline to add data to KG
upon publication

Credits for entries and maintenance

Communication within/between NFDIs

Figure 14: Ontologies and Knowledge Graphs